

Basic documentation for six semantically tagged Europarl v7 data files

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Language	Sentences	Words	Words/sentence (counted from the figures)
Czech	668,595	13,195,311	19.74
Spanish	2,123,835	54,806,927	25.82
Finnish	2,119,515	33,708,706	15.90
Italian	2,081,669	50,259,169	24.14
Portuguese	2,121,889	52,300,149	24.65
Swedish	2,241,386	45,665,947	20.37

Table 1. Europarl v7 data (<https://www.statmt.org/europarl/>)

Lexicons for the semantic taggers

<https://github.com/UCREL/Multilingual-USAS>

Fig. 1 Number of lexemes in each tagger's lexicon

	Number of lexemes in tagger's lexicon	Lexical coverage in Europarl v7
Czech	28 162	83.90%
Finnish	42 226	92.88%
Italian	33 098	94.06%
Portuguese	13 942	76.97%
Spanish	9 709	85.54%
Swedish	18 082	83.90%

Table 2. Lexical coverage of the six taggers with Europarl v7 texts of each language

Part of speech tagger used prior to semantic tagging

Treetagger: <https://www.cis.uni-muenchen.de/~schmid/tools/TreeTagger/>